

Research article

‘Rice,’ ‘sorghum,’ ‘pearl millet’ and ‘finger millet’ in Nilo-Saharan

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Abstract: This study overviews the geographical distribution of the terms for four major types of crops cultivated in Africa, ‘rice,’ ‘sorghum,’ ‘pearl millet’ and ‘finger millet’ in Nilo-Saharan languages. Most Nilo-Saharan languages lack a native term for ‘rice,’ but a number of languages attest a loanword from Arabic or Swahili. On the other hand, these languages attest a (possibly) native terms for ‘sorghum,’ ‘pearl millet’ and ‘finger millet,’ and we will analyze them by heuristically reconstructing proto-forms.*

Keywords: rice; sorghum; pearl millet; finger millet; Nilo-Saharan

1. Introduction

This study aims at surveying terms for crops to supplement related articles in *Language Atlas of Asia* (Endo et al. eds. 2021), which includes articles for ‘rice plant,’ and *Language Atlas of Asia and Africa II* (Suzuki et al. eds. 2023), which includes articles for ‘broomcorn millet,’ ‘foxtail millet’ and ‘barnyard millet’. Since broomcorn millet, foxtail millet and barnyard millet are not widely cultivated in Africa, we analyze terms for sorghum, finger millet and pearl millet that are more common in the regions (see Fukushima et al. eds. 2023 for the reference of linguistic data used for this study). In this study, heuristically reconstructed roots are marked by #.

2. ‘Rice’

Most Nilo-Saharan languages do not attest a native term for ‘rice’, but a number of them attest a loanword from a local *lingua franca*, namely Arabic (Type A, mostly via

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Sudanese Arabic *ruzz* or Chadian Arabic *rizz*, itself a Wanderwort related to Indian roots, cf. Sanskrit *vrihi*) and Swahili (Type B, the standard form is *mchele*, an Indo-Aryan loanword, cf. Hindi/Urdu *cāval*). Saharan languages Kanuri and Tudaga attest a form similar to the major Chadic (Afroasiatic) language of the area, Hausa *shìnkāfā* (Type C), which is possibly in fact a borrowing from Hausa.

Three Western Nilotic languages attest a native term heuristically reconstructed as *#lab* (Type D, Dinka *lop*, Shilluk *alabo* ‘rice grain’ and Anuak *alumo* ‘wild rice’), which resembles Nuer (Western Nilotic) *laap* ‘wheat’, Kuliak Ik *reba* ‘finger millet’ and the possible root for ‘sorghum’ in some other Western Nilotic and Surmic languages (*#labi*). Shilluk is unique among Nilo-Saharan in that it distinguishes between the term for ‘rice grain’ (*alabo*) and ‘rice plant’ (*peth*).

As for the other native terms (Type E), Dar Daju Daju in Chad attests *kasalange* and Zarma in Niger attests *mo*.

Fig. 1 ‘Rice’ in Nilo-Saharan

Table 1 Signs for Fig. 1

- | A: Arabic borrowing
- B: Swahili borrowing
- △ C: possible Hausa borrowing
- D: *#lab*
- E: the other native terms

3. ‘Sorghum’

Sorghum (or guinea corn, sometimes glossed *dura*, a Sudanese Arabic term) is one of the main crops in Sudanic Africa and is attested with various native terms.

Type A #*bel* is commonly attested in Western Nilotic (Reel *beel*, Kumam *bel*, Shilluk *byel*) and could be related to Dinka (Western Nilotic) *bel* ‘durra cane’. Notably, two Central Sudanic languages attest it (Kara *bila*, Yulu *abeel*) probably due to contact.

Type B #*mwa* is common in Eastern Nilotic (Bari *kima*, Otuho *nema*, Turkana *emwae*). Songhay Zarma also attests a similar form *haamo* (compare with Zarma *mo* ‘rice’), but its resemblance with Eastern Nilotic might be coincidental.

Type C #*kari* is commonly attested in Taman (Tama *kari-t*, Abu Sharib *koriñen*) and is also attested in a Saharan language (Zaghawa *gure*).

Type D #*labi* is attested in Surmic (Murle *labitot*, Suri *liway*, Kwegu *ruub*) and Western Sudanic (Dinka *rap*). Compare with Kuliak Ik *reba* ‘finger millet’, Western Nilotic Nuer *laap* ‘wheat’ and the possible Western Nilotic root #*lab* ‘rice’.

Three other types are attested in only one branch. Type E #*jana* (adopted from **jana* by Otero 2019) is commonly attested in Koman, Type F #*mony* in Central Sudanic (Bongo *mony*, Beli *manya*, Jur-Modo *nyonyu*) and Type G #*kunj* in Daju (Dar Daju *kuñje*, Shatt *kuc*). The other terms (Type H) are attested in only one language.

Fig. 2 ‘Sorghum’ in Nilo-Saharan

Table 2 Signs for Fig. 2

	A: # <i>bel</i>
—	B: # <i>mwa</i>
☆	C: # <i>kari</i>
△	D: # <i>labi</i>
◇	E: # <i>jana</i>
×	F: # <i>mony</i>
□	G: # <i>kunj</i>
●	H: the other native terms

4. ‘Pearl millet’

As for pearl millet (bulrush millet, Sudanese Arabic *duxun*), four roots can be heuristically reconstructed.

Type A #*ta’ba* is attested in a Central Sudanic language Yulu (*ta’ba*) and two closely related Eastern Nilotic Maa languages (Chamus *n-tapa*, Samburu *ntapa*). Their resemblance could be merely coincidental.

Type B #*kurwec* is attested in the Daju branch (Dar Daju Daju *kuruce*, Shatt *gurwec* ‘millet’) and the Eastern Nilotic language Bari (*kureja*). Compare with Saharan Zaghawa *gure* ‘sorghum’ and the common Taman root #*kari* ‘sorghum’.

Type C #*kel* is attested in two Central Sudanic languages (Bongo *kel*, Baka *keli*). It resembles the root #*kal* ‘finger millet’ attested in Southern Lwo (Western Nilotic), but their etymological relation is obscure.

Type D #*rau* is attested in Eastern Nilotic Turkana (*erau*) and Western Nilotic Lwo (Acoli *raa*, Belanda Bor *raw* ‘millet’, Pări *rau* ‘millet’).

Fig. 3 'Pearl millet' in Nilo-Saharan

Table 3 Signs for Fig. 3

- | A: #*ta'ba*
- B: #*kurwec*
- △ C: #*kel*
- D: #*rau*
- F: the other native terms

5. ‘Finger millet’

As for finger millet (eleusine, Sudanese Arabic *talabūn*), three possible roots are given on the map. Each one is attested in only one branch.

Type A *#k(p)aya* is attested in Central Sudanic (Baka *koyo*, Jur-Modo *kpaya* ‘petit mil’, Yulu *kayə* ‘petit mil’).

Type B *#kima* is attested in Eastern Nilotic (Turkana *akimait*, Karamojong *a-kima-it*). Another Eastern Nilotic language, Bari, attests *kima* ‘sorghum’.

Type C *#kal* is attested in Southern Lwo (Kumam *kal*, Acoli *kal*), which resembles Central Sudanic *#kel* ‘pearl millet’.

Fig. 4 ‘Finger millet’ in Nilo-Saharan

Table 4 Signs for Fig. 3

- | A: *#k(p)aya*
- B: *#kima*
- △ D: *#kal*
- F: the other native terms

References

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